

GROWING STUDENT LITERACY ABILITY THROUGH THE SCHOOL LITERACY MOVEMENT

Dodo

Madrasah Supervisor of the Ministry of Religion of Ciamis Regency

Email: do2spd@gmail.com

Abstract

In today's rapidly evolving world, literacy has become an essential skill for individuals to navigate and succeed in various aspects of life. Literacy is not limited to reading and writing but also encompasses critical thinking, comprehension, and communication skills. Recognizing the significance of literacy, many educational institutions and organizations have initiated programs and movements to enhance the literacy capabilities of students. One such movement is the School Literacy Movement. This study aims to explore gerakan literasi sekolah and its impact on the growth of students' literacy skills.

Keywords: Literacy, Comprehension, Critical Thinking.

Submission Date: 1 Juli 2023

Revised Date: 29 July 2023

Accepted Date: 31 July 2023

INTRODUCTION

Literacy is no longer limited to the ability to read and write. In today's digital era, students need multiple literacy to navigate and excel in various domains. The School Literacy Movement has emerged as a comprehensive approach to building students' skills through diverse literacy, including literacy, numerical literacy, scientific literacy, financial literacy, digital literacy, and cultural and civic literacy.

Literacy in English is written literacy, this word comes from the Latin littera (letters) which has a definition involving mastery of writing systems and the conventions that accompany them. With regards to this (Kern, 2000) defines the term literacy comprehensively as follows: Literacy is the use of socially, historically, and culturally located practices to create and interpret meaning through text. This requires at least a tacit awareness of the relationship between textual conventions and the context in which they are used and, ideally, an ability to critically reflect on those relationships. Because it is purpose-sensitive, literacy is dynamic – not static – and variable across and within discourse communities and cultures. It draws on a range of cognitive abilities, on knowledge of written and spoken language, knowledge of genres, and knowledge of culture. While the definition of literacy according to (Unisco, 2023) as reported on its official website: Literacy is a series of learning and proficiency in reading, writing, and using numbers throughout life and is part of a larger skill set, which includes digital skills, media literacy, education for sustainable development, and global citizenship, as well as skills job specific. From the statement above it can be seen that literacy requires

complex abilities. The knowledge of genre is knowledge of the types of texts used in the discourse community, for example, narrative texts, expositions, descriptions and others.

In the implementation of the School Literacy Movement, (Pangesti Wiedarti, dkk, 2018) explained that the school literacy movement is a participatory effort or activity by involving school members (students, teachers, school principals, education staff, school supervisors, school committees, parents/guardians of students), academics, publishers, mass media, community (community leaders who can represent exemplary, the business world, etc.), and stakeholders under the coordination of the Directorate General of Primary and Secondary Education, Ministry of Education and Culture. In the master book of the School Literacy Movement Master Design (Edition 2 Print 1: October 2018) by (Pangesti Wiedarti, dkk, 2018), that the school literacy movement is a social movement with the collaborative support of various elements. One of the steps taken to realize the school as a learning organization whose citizens are literate throughout life is the habit of reading students. This habituation is carried out with a 15-minute reading activity (the teacher reads a book and/or students and the teacher read silently, which is adjusted to the context or school targets).

Furthermore, the government issued a complete guide regarding the school literacy movement, namely: the Guidebook for the School Literacy Movement in Elementary Schools (Roosie Setiawan, dkk, 2019); Handbook of the School Literacy Movement in Junior High Schools (Pratiwi Retnaningdyah, dkk, 2019); Handbook of the School Literacy Movement in High Schools (Marni Hartati, dkk, 2020). This study aims to explore the strategies for implementing the School Literacy Movement and its impact on students' literacy skills as a whole based on research results from various school levels.

METHODOLOGY

In order to get an overview of how to implement the School Literacy Movement in shaping students' literacy skills at school, researchers used the literature study method. The procedures carried out in this method include, 1) identifying research topics, 2) formulating research questions, 3) determining library sources, 4) conducting information searches, 5) selecting and filtering the literature collections obtained, 6) reviewing and analyzing literature, 7) organizing and synthesizing information, 8) evaluating library sources, and 9) synthesizing and writing. These steps are as follows (Margono, 2009) explained that to get to know the literature or data sources that can be used as a reference there are basic standards that must be considered by researchers as follows: 1) Studying what results have been or have been obtained by other people in the research field concerned. 2) Study the research methods that have been used, including sampling methods, data collection methods, data sources, units of measure and criteria. 3) Collect data from other existing sources related to the research project to be carried out. 4) Study the descriptive and historical factors that exist and are the background of future problems. 5) Study the deductive analysis of problems that have been done by others.

The procedure carried out in this method is in line with what was said by (Creswell, 2015) that literature review is a written summary of articles from journals, books, and other documents that describe theory and information both past and present, organizes literature into topics

and documents needed for research proposals, while (Taylor, D. Procter, M, 2010) explained that a literature review or also called a literature review (literature review) is an activity to review or review various literature that has been published by academics or other researchers previously related to the topic that we will examine. In line with this (L Towne, RJ Shavelson, 2002) explained that compiling a literature review is the same as summarizing various previous research results to get an overview of the topic or problem to be studied as well as to answer the various challenges that arise when starting a research.

Another opinion from (Sugiyono, 2010) defines literature study as a research method that is carried out by collecting various references or library materials, then analyzing, synthesizing, and interpreting these materials to support and compile scientific work. Then from (Arikunto, 2010) states that literature study is an activity to find and collect information from various library materials related to research problems, which are then used as reference materials for compiling scientific writing. Meanwhile, (Thomas, 2009) defines literature study as an analysis of materials that are relevant to a particular topic. It involves critical reading, synthesis and presentation of information from multiple sources to come up with a comprehensive understanding of the topic.

In line with that, (Miles dan Huberman, 1992) explained that literature study is a systematic process for collecting, identifying, selecting, reading, and evaluating literature or library materials that are relevant to the research problem or research question posed. This opinion is confirmed by (Umar, 2011) who states that literature study is a systematic effort to obtain information, gain an in-depth understanding of a topic, and utilize relevant literature to support the formulation of problems or frameworks in research.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results

After going through the process which became a research procedure using the literature study method, the researcher found the results of this study in the form of a clear picture of the implementation of the school literacy movement carried out in schools and its impact on student literacy. The researcher found twenty studies published in scientific periodicals that have an International Standard Serial Number (ISSN) and a national reputation, namely: 1) (Ramandanu, 2019), 2) (Kartika Megantara, Abdul Wachid BS, 2021), 3) (Liana Hasni, A. Hari Witono, Baiq Niswatul Khair, 2022), 4) (Fahimatul Anis, Siti Bariroh, 2020), 5) (Kastro, 2020), 6) (Iin Puspasari, Febrina Dafit, 2021), 7) (Widodo, 2020), 8) (Syahidin, 2020), 9) (Mhd Rizkiy Bahar Siregar, Annisa Dahlila Angelina, Maisarah Maisarah, Liza Annisa, Mardianto Mardianto, Haidir Haidir, 2022), 10) (Muh. Arafik, Titis Angga Rini, 2021), 11) (Yossinta Intaniasari, Ratnasari Dyah Utami, 2022), 12) (Febri Firmansyah, Dassucik Dassucik, Tri Astindari, 2023), 13) (Sardani Sardani, Khairuddin Khairuddin, Nasir Usman, 2021), 14) (El Frisa Yunita Anindya, Sri Suneki, Verylina Purnamasari, 2019), 15) (Jatnika, 2019), 16) (Muhammad Hilal Hidayat, Imam Agus Basuki, Sa'dun Akbar, 2018), 17) (Sunu Hastuti, Nia Agus Lestari, 2018), 18) (Sari, 218), 19) (Billy

Antoro, Endry Boeriswati, Eva Leiliyanti, 2021), 20) (Ahmad Yulianto, Syams Kusumaningrum, Elma Fitriani Polan, 2022). This is what researchers do in order to meet research standards with the literature study method where the literature materials processed by researchers are relevant and accountable. In the following, the researcher presents interesting findings from the results of this study.

Table 1
Research Findings

No.	Author	Research Title	Research Objectives	Results and Discussion	Accreditation
1.	Febriana Ramandanu	School Literacy Movement Through Utilization of Classroom Reading Corners as an Alternative Means of Growing Students' Interest in Reading	Researchers are interested in perfecting previous research by conducting research with the title "School Literacy Movement through the use of classroom reading corners as an alternative means of growing students' reading interest	The results showed that the implementation of the School Literacy Movement at Pamongan 2 Public Elementary School, Guntur District, Demak Regency had been able to foster students' interest in reading with the School Literacy Movement program through the use of reading corners in each class.	Sinta 2
2.	Kartika Megantara, Abdul Wachid BS	Reading Habits in Indonesian Lessons Through the School Literacy Movement	The ultimate goal of this research is to describe and analyze various activities related to the School Literacy Movement as an effort to foster reading habits in MI Muhammadiyah Penaruban.	Based on the data obtained through several methods, the researcher concluded that the activities of the School Literacy Movement at MI Muhammadiyah Penaruban, Purbalingga Regency, were going well and were beneficial for students in cultivating the habit	Sinta 3

No.	Author	Research Title	Research Objectives	Results and Discussion	Accreditation
				of reading as a part of literacy.	
3.	Liana Hasni, A. Hari Witono, Bai q Niswatul Khair	The Role of the Teacher in Creating a Literacy Culture Through the School Literacy Movement in Grade IV MI Darul Hikmah Darek	This study aims to find out about the teacher's role in implementing the School Literacy Movement in class IV MI Darul Hikmah Darek	Based on the research results, the teacher's role in the School Literacy Movement has been carried out in accordance with the government's program which consists of habituation stages, development stages, and learning stages. The role of the teacher that has been carried out in the habituation stage includes reading 15 minutes before learning begins, arranging literacy-rich infrastructure and environment, creating an environment with literacy nuances. And the role of the teacher in the development stage that has been carried out includes integrated reading, reading together, discussing books. Whereas at the learning stage it has not been implemented at MI	Sinta 4

No.	Author	Research Title	Research Objectives	Results and Discussion	Accreditation
				Darul Hikmah Darek.	
4.	Fahimatul Anis, Siti Bariroh	Growing Students' Interest in Literacy in Schools Through the School Literacy Movement	The objectives expected in this study are (1) Implement strategies to foster student literacy in the school environment (2) Describe the benefits of literacy for students in schools.	The growth of literacy in schools can be done through routine activities and incidental activities. These activities are carried out in three stages of literacy, namely the stages of habituation, development, and learning	Sinta 6
5.	Alexander Kastro	The Role of the School Library as a Supporting Facility for the School Literacy Movement in Junior High Schools	The purpose of this study is to describe the form of implementation of the School Literacy Movement in Petama Middle School (SMP).	The findings from this study are that literacy activities have a role in increasing students' interest in reading and writing. This activity also made students interested in participating in various competitions held by the school and external parties with a full sense of responsibility.	Sinta 5
6.	Iin Puspasari, Febrina Dafit	Implementation of the School Literacy Movement in Elementary Schools	This study aims to describe habituation inside and outside the classroom Literacy Movement at SDN 006 Simpang Perak Jaya	There are several habits in the class such as reading 15 minutes, magazines and exchanging books between classes. While the habituation outside the classroom is reading garden	Sinta 5

No.	Author	Research Title	Research Objectives	Results and Discussion	Accreditation
				visits and library visits	
7.	Antoni Widodo	Implementation of the School Literacy Movement Program in Junior High Schools (SMP)	This article aims to find out the implementation of the School Literacy Movement program at SMP IT Insan Harapan, South Tangerang City.	The results of the study show that the School Literacy Movement has not been carried out routinely. Efforts made by schools to support the Literacy Movement 1) Providing a variety of reading books 2) Making 2 hours of reading activities on Fridays 3) carrying out 15 minutes of reading before learning starts 4) creating a computer laboratory (school internet cafe)	Sinta 2
8.	Syahidin	Increasing Interest in Reading through the School Literacy Movement	Through the reading literacy movement it is hoped that students will be able to develop and stimulate their reading literacy skills, creativity, imagination, and also their knowledge.	With the seriousness and cooperation of all related parties, the Literacy Culture Program at Northeast Bunguran 1 Public High School can be realized which will eventually bring big changes with the emergence of generations who will always use information to make changes.	Sinta 4

No.	Author	Research Title	Research Objectives	Results and Discussion	Accreditation
9.	Mhd Rizkiy Bahar Siregar, Annisa Dahlila Angelina, Maisarah, Deagi Nur Mohamad Liza Annisa4, Mardianto5 Haidir	The Role of Literacy in Reading and Writing in Fostering Students' Interest in Reading at Public Madrasah Tsanawiyyah	Aims to increase students' interest in books even though it is only a sheet and frees them to read any book.	The results of the analysis of this study indicate that the reading literacy activities carried out by MTsN 2 Medan schools provide good results and the growing interest in reading and writing of students, the School Literacy Movement at MTsN 2 Medan is also supported by various extracurriculars at school such as Arabic Club, English Club, Tahfidz Qur'an	Sinta 3
10.	Muh. Arafik, Titis Angga Rini	Development of the Implementation of the Children's Literacy Movement Can Grow Elementary School Students' Interest in Reading?	This study aims to identify, describe and give deep meaning to all activities of the Child Literacy Movement at the development stage in order to foster elementary school students' interest in reading.	The results showed that Child Literacy Movement activities at the development stage were carried out through (1) children's literature literacy celebrations, (2) children's literature literacy pockets, (3) library visits, (4) independent reading of children's literature.	Sinta 3

No.	Author	Research Title	Research Objectives	Results and Discussion	Accreditation
11.	Yossinta Intaniasari, Ratnasari Dyah Utami	Growing Student Reading Culture Through Digital Literacy in Learning and School Literacy Programs	The aims of this research are 1) to formulate the implementation of digital literacy in learning and school literacy programs to foster students' reading culture, and 2) to analyze the obstacles in implementing digital literacy in learning during a pandemic.	The results of the study showed that 1) all schools have implemented digital literacy in learning, and integrated IT even though it has not been fully maximized, teachers utilize learning media and applications such as Zoom, Google Classroom, WAG, and Youtube, with digital literacy can foster students' reading culture during their childhood. pandemic. The school literation movement program has been implemented, although not as optimal as it was before the pandemic. 2) Obstacles to implementing digital literacy include limited infrastructure, internet connection, students who do not yet have a smartphone and low human resources.	Sinta 5

No.	Author	Research Title	Research Objectives	Results and Discussion	Accreditation
12.	Febri Firmansyah, Dassucik, Dassucik, Tri Astindari	The Role of the Teacher in Growing the Literacy Ability of Class VII Students at MTs Miftahul Hidayah Gayam Lor Bondowoso Even Semester 2021/2022 Academic Year	The objectives of this study were to: (1) Know the literacy skills of students in class VII lesson planning at MTs Miftahul Hidayah Gayam Lor Bondowoso even semester of the 2021/2022 academic year. (2) Knowing the teacher's role in fostering student literacy in the learning process for class VII at MTs Miftahul Hidayah Gayam Lor Bondowoso even semester of the 2021/2022 school year.	The results of the research obtained in the literacy movement are that the role of the teacher at MTs Miftahul Hidayah Gayam Lor is carried out through planning and processes which are then implemented in the stages of habituation, development and learning	Sinta 5
13.	Sardani, Sardani, Khairuddin, Khairuddin, Nasir, Usman	Management of the School Literacy Movement Program in Growing Interest in Reading for Elementary School Students in Cluster 1 Indrapuri Aceh Besar	This study aims to describe: (1) literacy movement program planning; (2) implementing the school literacy movement; (3) evaluating the implementation of the school literacy movement. This study uses a qualitative approach and descriptive method. The subjects of this study consisted of school principals, school committees,	The results of this study are: (1) The planning for the School Literacy Movement program has been well prepared and takes into account the provisions issued by the Ministry of Education and Culture in 2015 to foster students' interest in reading; (2) Implementation of the School Literacy Movement program at SD	Sinta 3

No.	Author	Research Title	Research Objectives	Results and Discussion	Accreditation
			teachers, head of librarians and students at SD Cluster 1 Indrapuri Aceh Besar.	Cluster 1 Indrapuri is in accordance with literacy program standards, and is experiencing problems with limited reading materials at school; (3) The results of the evaluation of the School Literacy Movement program activities at SD Cluster 1 Indrapuri Aceh Besar showed that most of the students had increased their interest in reading, although there were still some students who had not been able to make resumes and create their own work.	
14	El Frisa Yunita Anindya, Sri Suneki, Veryliana Purnamasari	Analysis of the School Literacy Movement in Thematic Learning	The researcher intends to conduct research on the school literacy movement in thematic learning at SD N Kandang Panjang 10 Pekalongan	The results showed that the implementation of the School Literacy Movement was known from the results of filling out the questionnaire by all high school students at SD N Kandang Panjang 10 Pekalongan at the habituation stage (55.8%) in the good category. The	Sinta 2

No.	Author	Research Title	Research Objectives	Results and Discussion	Accreditation
				criteria for learning stages are in the good category (72.92%). Adequate facilities and infrastructure with a reading corner in each classroom with a collection of books that vary, school corridors have posters, and bulletin boards are available to place student writings.	
15.	Shiva Ardenia Jatnika	Literacy Culture to Grow Interest in Reading and Writing	This writing aims to find out how the role of literacy culture in social life in today's modern era will continue to be eroded by technological developments.	The result is to foster an interest in reading and writing, it must require several roles, such as infrastructure in schools, the community and parents. If the role is inadequate, it will have a negative impact on the continuation of a good literacy culture.	Sinta 4
16	Muhammad Hilal Hidayat, Imam Agus Basuki, Sa'dun Akbar	School Literacy Movement in Elementary Schools	This study describes the implementation of the School Literacy Movement at SDN 2 Sitirejo and SDN 4 Panggungrejo.	The results showed that the implementation of the school literacy movement in the two schools had not been carried out optimally because there were still several inhibiting	Sinta 3

No.	Author	Research Title	Research Objectives	Results and Discussion	Accreditation
				factors that were still not resolved so that they did not have a positive impact on students' reading enthusiasm, this was indicated by the lack of visibility of students' reading activities while in school. in the school environment.	
17.	Sunu Hastuti, Nia Agus Lestari	School Literacy Movement: Implementation of the Literacy Familiarization and Development Stage in SD Sukorejo, Kediri	This study seeks to describe information about the implementation of the School Literacy Movement at SD Sukorejo, Gurah District, Kediri Regency, especially at the habituation stage.	The results of the study show that at SD Sukorejo Gurah Kediri, the application of literacy is still at the habituation stage. The school's efforts to activate the literacy movement are by getting used to reading non-learning books 15 minutes before class starts, organizing an environment that supports literacy and involving partners in implementing literacy activities.	Sinta 5

No.	Author	Research Title	Research Objectives	Results and Discussion	Accreditation
18.	Ika Fadilah Ratna Sari	The Basic Concept of the School Literacy Movement In the Minister of Education and Culture Regulation Number 23 of 2015 Concerning the Growth of Character and Character	The purpose of this research is to analyze the basic concept of school literacy in the Minister of Education and Culture Regulation Number 23 of 2015 concerning the Growth of Character and Character.	Based on the results of data analysis it can be concluded as follows: (1) literacy is the ability to use language and images in rich and varied forms to read, write, listen, speak, see, present and think critically about ideas so as to be able to explain social practices and the culture and meaning contained by being oriented towards print texts as well as multidimensional and interactive critically; (2) the literacy component consists of early literacy, basic literacy, library literacy, media literacy, technology literacy, and visual literacy; 15 minutes before class starts; and (4) the SCHOOL LITERACY MOVEMENT can be seen from several perspectives, including in terms of education, communication, culture, language, cognitive,	Sinta 2

No.	Author	Research Title	Research Objectives	Results and Discussion	Accreditation
				knowledge growth and Islam.	
19.	Billy Antoro, Endry Boeriswati, Eva Leiliyanti	Implementation of the School Literacy Movement in Junior High Schools	This study aims to evaluate the implementation of the school literacy movement program at SMP Negeri 107 Jakarta.	In conclusion, the habituation of literacy activities in schools in the form of a 15 minute reading program, coupled with a literacy-rich physical environment and the use of literacy strategies in learning are proven to be able to shape students' new skills.	Sinta 4
20.	Ahmad Yulianto, Syams Kusumaningrum, Elma Fitriani Polan	The Impact of the School Literacy Movement on Reading Interest in Elementary School Students	This study aims to determine the effect of the School Literacy Movement movement on reading interest in class III students at SD Negeri 2 Remu, Sorong City.	The increase in the reading interest of Remu 2 Public Elementary School students, Sorong City, illustrates that the school is successful and has met the standards in carrying out the school literacy movement	Sinta 4

Source: Sinta accredited journal

Discussion

Researchers took data from research results published in National Journals as many as 20 samples that had been accredited by Sinta 2 in four journals, Sinta 3 in five journals, Sinta 4 in five journals, Sinta 5 in five journals, and Sinta 6 in one journal. The results of this study were taken from various levels of school, for the SD/MI level there were 12 institutions, the SMP/MTs level were 5 institutions, the SMA level was 1 institution, and the Higher Education level was 2 institutions.

From the research data, it can be concluded that the implementation of the School Literacy Movement can make a significant contribution to the overall development of students by equipping them with a variety of literacy. However, several challenges need to be overcome to ensure successful implementation. These challenges include resistance from traditional education systems, a lack of resources and infrastructure, and the need for ongoing teacher training and support. To overcome these challenges, it is important to involve all stakeholders, including policy makers, educators, parents and the community, in the implementation process. Collaboration, effective communication, and ongoing evaluation are critical to the success of a sustainable school literacy movement.

Research related to literacy in schools must continue to be developed, because this is in line with government programs, student literacy activities in schools are in accordance with the steps for implementing the School Literacy Movement. These activities include: 1) Habituation (growing a culture of literacy and interest in reading in schools, one of which is through a 15-minute reading activity); 2) Development (development of literacy skills through non-academic activities, for example extracurricular activities and mandatory visits to the library (literacy hours)); 3) Habituation (Intracurricular activities/learning using literacy strategies). This research is only limited to looking at the description of the implementation of student literacy in schools in implementing the National Literacy Movement (GLN) program through the School Literacy Movement, so that there are opportunities for other researchers to conduct more comprehensive studies on other aspects in the context of various literacy.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the research that the researchers took from 20 sample journals that discussed student literacy with the School Literacy Movement, it can be concluded that the School Literacy Movement provides a holistic approach to developing students' abilities through various literacy. By implementing school literacy movement strategies such as integrated curricula, teacher training, collaborative approaches, technology integration, and assessment and feedback mechanisms, students can improve literacy, numerical literacy, scientific literacy, financial literacy, digital literacy, and cultural literacy and citizenship. The benefits of implementing the school literacy movement include holistic development, real-world relevance, empowerment, and equality and inclusion. However, overcoming challenges

and ensuring collaboration among all stakeholders is critical for the successful implementation of the school literacy movement and its long-term impact on students' lives.

References

- Ahmad Yulianto, Syams Kusumaningrum, Elma Fitriani Polan. (2022). Dampak GLS (Gerakan Literasi Sekolah) terhadap Minat Baca Peserta Didik Sekolah Dasar. *Jurnal Papeda: Jurnal Publikasi Pendidikan Dasar*, 4(2), 125-131. Diambil kembali dari <https://unimuda.e-journal.id/jurnalpendidikdasar/article/view/2652>
- Arikunto, S. (2010). *Metode peneltian*. Jakarta: Rineka Cipta.
- Billy Antoro, Endry Boeriswati, Eva Leiliyanti. (2021). Pelaksanaan Gerakan Literasi Sekolah di Sekolah Menengah Pertama. *Jurnal Kajian Bahasa, Sastra dan Pengajaran (KIBASP)*, 5(1), 1-15. Diambil kembali dari <https://journal.ipm2kpe.or.id/index.php/KIBASP/article/view/2474>
- Creswell, J. W. (2015). *Educational research: Planning, conducting, and evaluating quantitative and qualitative research* (Kindle edition ed.). Pearson Education.
- El Frisa Yunita Anindya, Sri Suneki, Veryliana Purnamasari. (2019). Analisis Gerakan Literasi Sekolah Pada Pembelajaran Tematik. *Jurnal Ilmiah Sekolah Dasar*, 3(2), 238–245. Diambil kembali dari <https://ejournal.undiksha.ac.id/index.php/JISD/article/view/18053>
- Fahimatul Anis, Siti Bariroh. (2020). Menumbuhkan Minat Literasi Siswa Di Sekolah Melalui Gerakan Literasi Sekolah. *Jurnal Ilmiah Jendela Pendidikan*, 9(2), 5-24. Diambil kembali dari <https://journal.unigres.ac.id/index.php/JendelaPendidikan/article/view/1055>
- Febri Firmansyah, Dassucik Dassucik, Tri Astindari. (2023). Peran Guru Dalam Menumbuhkan Kemampuan Literasi Siswa Kelas VII di Mts Miftahul Hidayah Gayam Lor Bondowoso Semester Genap Tahun Pelajaran 2021/2022. *Jurnal Pendidikan, Sains Dan Teknologi*, 10(2), 381-391. Diambil kembali dari <https://journalstkipgrisitubondo.ac.id/index.php/EDUSAINTEK/article/view/583>
- Iin Puspasari, Febrina Dafit. (2021). Implementasi Gerakan Literasi Sekolah di Sekolah Dasar. *Jurnal Basicedu*, 5(3), 1390-1400. Diambil kembali dari <https://jbasic.org/index.php/basicedu/article/view/939>
- Jatnika, S. A. (2019). Budaya Literasi untuk Menumbuhkan Minat Membaca dan Menulis. *Indonesian Journal of Primary Education*, 3(2), 1-6. Diambil kembali dari <https://ejournal.upi.edu/index.php/IJPE/article/view/18112>
- Kartika Megantara, Abdul Wachid BS. (2021). Pembiasaan Membaca dalam Pelajaran Bahasa Indonesia Melalui Gerakan Literasi Sekolah. *Jurnal Onoma: Pendidikan, Bahasa, Dan Sastra*, 7(2), 383-390. Diambil kembali dari <https://e-journal.my.id/onoma/article/view/1230>

- Kastro, A. (2020). Peranan Perpustakaan Sekolah sebagai Sarana Pendukung Gerakan Literasi Sekolah di Sekolah Menengah Pertama. *Jurnal Kajian Pembelajaran dan Keilmuan*, 4(1), 92-100. Diambil kembali dari <https://jurnal.untan.ac.id/index.php/jurnalkpk/article/view/40887>
- Kern, R. (2000). *Literacy and Language Teaching*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- L Towne, RJ Shavelson. (2002). *Scientific research in education*. National Academy Press Publications Sales Office.
- Liana Hasni , A. Hari Witono, Baiq Niswatul Khair. (2022). Peran Guru Dalam Menciptakan Budaya Literasi Melalui Gerakan Literasi Sekolah (GLS) di Kelas IV MI Darul Hikmah Darek. *Journal of Classroom Action Research*, 4(3), 60-66. Diambil kembali dari <https://jppipa.unram.ac.id/index.php/jcar/article/view/1893>
- Margono, S. (2009). *Metodologi Penelitian Pendidikan Komponen MKDK*. Jakarta: PT Rineka Cipta.
- Marni Hartati, dkk. (2020). *Panduan Gerakan Literasi Sekolah di Sekolah Menengah Atas (Tahun 2020 Edisi Revisi)*. Jakarta: Diterbitkan oleh Direktorat Sekolah Menengah Atas.
- Mhd Rizkiy Bahar Siregar, Annisa Dahlila Angelina, Maisarah Maisarah, Liza Annisa, Mardianto Mardianto, Haidir Haidir. (2022). Peran Literasi Baca Tulis Dalam Menumbuhkan Minat Membaca Siswa di Madrasah Tsanawiyah Negeri. *Munaddhomah: Jurnal Manajemen Pendidikan Islam*, 3(2), 149-159. Diambil kembali dari <https://pasca.jurnalikhac.ac.id/index.php/munaddhomah/article/view/237>
- Miles dan Huberman. (1992). *Analisis data kualitatif: buku sumber tentang metode-metode baru*. Jakarta: UIP.
- Muh. Arafik, Titis Angga Rini. (2021). Pengembangan Implementasi Gerakan Literasi Sastra Anak Mampukah Menumbuhkan Minat Baca Siswa Sekolah Dasar? *Ilmu Pendidikan: Jurnal Kajian Teori dan Praktik Kependidikan*, 6(2), 75-84. Diambil kembali dari <https://journal2.um.ac.id/index.php/jktpk/article/view/26825>
- Muhammad Hilal Hidayat, Imam Agus Basuki, Sa'dun Akbar. (2018). Gerakan Literasi Sekolah di Sekolah Dasar. *Jurnal Pendidikan: Teori, Penelitian, dan Pengembangan*, 3(6), 810-817. Diambil kembali dari <https://journal.um.ac.id/index.php/jptpp/article/view/11213>
- Pangesti Wiedarti, dkk. (2018). *Desain Induk Gerakan Literasi Sekolah (Edisi 2 Cetakan 1: Oktober 2018)*. Jakarta: Direktorat Jenderal Pendidikan Dasar dan Menengah Kementerian Pendidikan dan Kebudayaan.
- Pratiwi Retnaningdyah, dkk. (2019). *Panduan Gerakan Literasi Sekolah di Sekolah Menengah Pertama (Cetakan 2: April 2019)*. Jakarta: Direktorat Pembinaan Sekolah Menengah

- Pertama, Direktorat Jenderal Pendidikan Dasar dan Menengah, Kementerian Pendidikan dan Kebudayaan.
- Ramandanu, F. (2019). Gerakan literasi sekolah (GLS) melalui pemanfaatan sudut baca kelas sebagai sarana alternatif penumbuhan minat baca siswa. *Mimbar Ilmu*, 24(1), 10-19. Diambil kembali dari <https://ejournal.undiksha.ac.id/index.php/MI/article/view/17405>
- Rosie Setiawan, dkk. (2019). *Panduan Gerakan Literasi Sekolah di Sekolah Dasar (Cetakan 1: Juni 2019)*. Jakarta: Direktorat Pembinaan Sekolah Dasar Direktorat Jenderal Pendidikan Dasar dan Menengah Kementerian Pendidikan dan Kebudayaan.
- Sardani Sardani, Khairuddin Khairuddin, Nasir Usman. (2021). Manajemen Program Gerakan Literasi Sekolah Dalam Menumbuhkan Minat Baca Siswa SD di Gugus 1 Indrapuri Aceh Besar. *Visipena*, 12(1), 17-29. Diambil kembali dari <https://ejournal.bbg.ac.id/visipena/article/view/1262>
- Sari, I. F. (218). Konsep Dasar Gerakan Literasi Sekolah Pada Permendikbud Nomor 23 Tahun 2015 Tentang Penumbuhan Budi Pekerti. *Al-Bidayah: Jurnal Pendidikan Dasar Islam*, 10(1), 89-100. Diambil kembali dari <https://jurnal.albidayah.id/home/article/view/131>
- Sugiyono. (2010). *Memahami Penelitian Kualitatif*.
- Sunu Hastuti, Nia Agus Lestari. (2018). Gerakan Literasi Sekolah: Implementasi Tahap Pembiasaan dan Pengembangan Literasi di SD Sukorejo Kediri. *Jurnal Basataka (JBT)*, 1(2), 29–34. Diambil kembali dari <https://jurnal.pbsi.uniba-bpn.ac.id/index.php/BASATAKA/article/view/34>
- Syahidin, S. (2020). Meningkatkan Minat Membaca melalui Gerakan Literasi Sekolah. *Asatiza: Jurnal Pendidikan*, 1(3), 373–380. Diambil kembali dari <https://ejournal.stai-tbh.ac.id/asatiza/article/view/163>
- Taylor, D. Procter, M. (2010). *The Literature Review: A Few Tips on Conducting It*. dimuat dalam laman University Toronto Writing Center.
- Thomas. (2009). Critical thinking, transformative learning, sustainable education, and problem-based learning in universities. *Journal of Transformative Education*, 7(3), 245-264.
- Umar. (2011). *Metode Penelitian Untuk Skripsi dan Tesis Bisnis* (11 ed.). Jakarta: PT Raja Grafindo Persada.
- Unisco. (2023, June 29). *Literacy*. Dipetik July 31, 2023, dari unesco: <https://www.unesco.org/en/literacy/need-know>

Widodo, A. (2020). Implementasi Program Gerakan Literasi Sekolah di Sekolah Menengah Pertama (SMP). *Tarbawi: Jurnal Ilmu Pendidikan*, 16(1), 11-21. Diambil kembali dari <http://ejournal.iainkerinci.ac.id/index.php/tarbawi/article/view/496>

Yossinta Intaniasari, Ratnasari Dyah Utami. (2022). Menumbuhkan Budaya Membaca Siswa Melalui Literasi Digital dalam Pembelajaran dan Program Literasi Sekolah. *Jurnal Basicedu*, 6(3), 4987-4998. Diambil kembali dari <https://jbasic.org/index.php/basicedu/article/view/2996>